

A Study on Job Satisfaction towards IT Employees in Coimbatore

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ABSTRACT

Happy workers are productive workers and productive workers are likely to be happy. Employee job satisfaction is essential to face the dynamic and ever-increasing challenges of maintaining productivity of the organization by keeping their workforce constantly engaged and motivated. Furthermore, environmental pressures, rising health costs and various needs of the workforce also pose a challenge for the management. This could be overcome by creating a work environment that maintains employee job satisfaction as well as motivates people towards exceptional performance at the workplace achieving work-life balance. This paper outlines the broad contours of various variables responsible for employee satisfaction and various ways by which one can maximize employee satisfaction.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, employees, factors, performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resource is considered to be the most valuable assets in any organization. It is the sum of total of inherent abilities acquired knowledge and skills represented by the talent and attitudes of employed persons who comprises of executives, supervisors, and rank and file of employees. It may be noted here that human resources should be utilized to the maximum possible extent, in order to achieve individual and organization goals. It is thus the employee's performance, which ultimately decides the attainment of goals. However the employee performance is to a large extent Influenced by motivation on job satisfaction.

Job Satisfaction is one of the important factors which have drawn attention of managers in the organization

as well as academicians. Whereas studies have been conducted to find out the factors which determine job satisfaction and the way it influences productivity in the organization.

Factors influencing of job satisfaction

Individual factors:

1. Level of education: It determines the degree of job satisfaction. Several studies have found negative correlation between the level of education, particularly higher level of education, and job satisfaction.

2. Age: Individual experience different degree of job satisfaction at different stages of their life.

3. Other factors: If an individual does not have favorable social and family life, he may not feel happy at the work life. Similarly other personal problems associated with him may affect his level of job satisfaction.

Nature of Job:

1. Occupational level: Higher level job provides more satisfaction as compare to lower level.

2. Job Content: It refers to the intrinsic value of the job which depends on the requirement of skills for performing it, and the degree of responsibility and growth it offers.

Situational variables:

1. Working conditions: It is particularly physical work environment, like conditions of place and associated facilities for performing the job.

2. **Supervision:** It affects Job satisfaction as in each type of supervision, the degree of Importance attached to individual variables.

3. **Equitable Rewards:** the type of linkage that is provided between job performance and rewards determine the degree of job satisfaction.

4. **Opportunity for promotion:** It is true that individual seek satisfaction in their jobs in the contest of job natures and work environment.

5. **Work group:** Individual works in group either created formally are the develop on their own to seek emotional satisfaction at their work place.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To identify the factors influence the job satisfaction of employees.
2. To identify the impact of employees' job satisfaction on their performance.
3. To identify the factors improve the satisfaction level of employees.

2.1 Scope of the study

1. To identify the employees level of satisfaction upon that job.
2. This study is helpful to that organization for conducting further research.
3. It is helpful to identify the employer's level of satisfaction towards welfare measure.
4. This study is helpful to the organization for identifying the area of dissatisfaction of job of the employees.
5. This study helps to make a managerial decision to the company.

2.2 Limitations of the study

1. The survey is subjected to the bias and prejudices of the respondents. Hence 100% accuracy can't be assured.
2. The researcher was carried out in a short span of time, where in the researcher could not widen the study.

3. The study could not be generalized due to the fact that researcher adapted personal interview method.

III. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The study was based on primary survey of 50 respondents belonging to Coimbatore, one of the largest and populated states of the Tamil Nadu, using a structured questionnaire. The socio-demographic profiles of the respondents were also recorded on the parameters such as gender, age, education level, occupation and Performance of employees. The questionnaire were designed to record the responses on Job satisfaction towards IT employees. Simple data analysis techniques were adopted such as descriptive statistics; using SPSS 20.0.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Harter et al. (2002)¹, has the authors conducted a met analysis of studies previously conducted by The Gallup Organization. The study examined aggregated employee job satisfaction sentiments and employee engagement, with the latter variable referring to individual involvement with as well as enthusiasm for work. Based on 7,939 business units in 36 organizations, the researchers found positive and substantive correlations between employee satisfaction-engagement and the business unit outcomes of productivity, profit, employee turnover, employee accidents, and customer satisfaction. More importantly, these researchers explored the practical utility of the observed relationships.

Kaliski (2007)², has Job satisfaction is a workers sense of achievement and success on the job of the employees in organization. Job satisfaction implies doing a job one enjoys, doing it well and being rewarded for one's efforts. Job satisfaction further implies enthusiasm and happiness with one's work. Job satisfaction is the key ingredient that leads to recognition, income, promotion, and the achievement of other goals that lead to a feeling of fulfillment.

George et al (2008)³, has Job satisfaction is the collection of feeling and beliefs that people have about their current job. People levels of degrees of job satisfaction can range from extreme satisfaction to extreme dissatisfaction. People also can have attitudes about various aspects of their jobs such as the kind of

work they do, their co-workers, supervisors or subordinates and their pay.

Jitendra Kumar Singh, Dr. Mini Jain (2013)⁴, Happy workers are productive workers and productive workers are likely to be happy. Employee job satisfaction is essential to face the dynamic and ever-increasing challenges of maintaining productivity of the organization by keeping their workforce constantly engaged and motivated. Furthermore, environmental pressures, rising health costs and various needs of the workforce also pose a challenge for the management. This could be overcome by creating a work environment that maintains employee job satisfaction as well as motivates people towards exceptional performance at the workplace achieving work-life balance. This paper outlines the broad contours of various variables responsible for employee satisfaction and various ways by which one can maximize employee satisfaction.

Aristovnik (2014)⁵, discusses influence of organizational and environmental factors on employee job satisfaction. The police employees rated salary and security as the least motivator and support from the management as high. Police employees rate trust and belongingness as the key factor to job satisfaction.

V. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 5.1

Demographic factors

		Frequency	Percent
Age	18-25	28	56
	26-35	6	12
	36-50	9	18
	50 above	7	14
	Total	50	100
Marital Status	Married	23	46
	Unmarried	27	54
	Total	50	100
Designation	Executive	12	24
	Senior Manager	9	18
	Team Leader	11	22
	Employee	18	36
	Total	50	100

From the above table no: 5.1 indicates that 56% of the respondents belong to 18-25 years of age and 18 % of the respondents to 36-50 years of age. This means that they were youngsters and middle-aged people. The employees of 54% of unmarried people and 46 % were married people.

Table 5.2: Employee job Satisfaction

Employee job Satisfaction		Frequency	Percent
Satisfaction of present job	Yes	29	58
	No	21	42
	Total	50	100
Salary offered at Company is sufficient to lead a satisfied life	Yes	33	66
	No	17	34
	Total	50	100
Satisfied with employment conditions prevailing in Organization	Yes	28	56
	No	22	44
	Total	50	100
Satisfied with the Physical Working Conditions	Yes	33	66
	No	17	34
	Total	50	100
Satisfied with relationship existing with subordinates and superiors	Yes	27	54
	No	23	46
	Total	50	100
Working Hours satisfactory	Yes	32	64
	No	18	36
	Total	50	100

The above table reveals that the 58% of highly satisfied about satisfied with your present job and 66 % of employees were salary being offered at company is sufficient to a lead satisfied life. The majority of the respondents of 56% of highly satisfied and 66% of employees were working with good conditions. The highest percentage of satisfied with relationship with subordinates and superiors.

Table 5.3 Motivates Efficiently/ Happily

Motivates Efficiently/ Happily	Frequency	Percent
Good Pay	26	52
Promotion	8	6
Less Supervision	13	26
Good Working Condition	3	16
Total	50	100

From the above table indicates that the 52% were good pay and 26% of employees were less supervision. The lowest percentage of employees was promotion.

Table 5.4: Satisfied with the way in which conflicts are resolved in your company

Satisfied of conflicts are resolved in your company	Frequency	Percent
Always	10	20
Quite Often	21	42
Some times	10	20
Rarely	7	14
Never	2	4
Total	50	100

The above table depicts that 42 % of employees were quite often and same percentage of employees were always and sometimes i.e 20%.

Table 5.5: Satisfied with the welfare measures

Satisfied with the welfare measures	Frequency	Percent
Medical Facilities	17	34
Compensation for accidents	7	14
Educational facilities for children	7	14
Transportation	19	38
Total	50	100

The above table shows that the highest percentage provided for transportation and 34 % of employees benefits for medical facilities.

Table 5.6 Satisfied with social security measures

Satisfied with social security measures	Frequency	Percent
Provident Fund	13	26
Pension	17	34
Gratuity	8	16
Bones	12	24
Total	50	100

From the above table shows that 34 % of employees were benefit for pensions and 26% of employees were provident fund.

VI. CONCLUSION

Any type of organizations exists without human beings. So, the job satisfaction of humanities is 'very important to the organization. In satisfaction a number of factors are considered such as personal factors, factors inherent in the job and factors controlled by the management. Besides the numerous theories of job satisfaction are involved. The majority of employees are satisfied with welfare measures. They should take necessary steps to solve problems in those measures so that the employee can do his job more effectively and felt that the working environment is better. Here the management should take necessary conditions and make the organization .the employees felt that they are satisfied with the bonus and provident fund given by the management.

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